

**ROYAL
BOTANIC
GARDEN
EDINBURGH**

**Royal Botanic Garden, Edinburgh (RBGE) and
Pollinating London Together (PLT)
Edinburgh Pollinator and Habitat Surveys
Report (2025)**

**AUTHOR & SURVEYOR:
Nicholas J Balfour**

**SUPERVISORS:
Caitlyn Johnstone
Emma Bush**

**POLLINATING
LONDON
TOGETHER**

Abstract

Urbanisation significantly impacts the presence, abundance, and distribution of pollinators worldwide. However, cities with ecologically healthy green spaces can play a significant role in supporting pollinator populations, acting as potential habitat refugia and offering diverse and continuous pollinator resources throughout the year.

In 2025, 31 green spaces in central Edinburgh, including allotments, public gardens, cemeteries and roof gardens, were surveyed to assess pollinator diversity and resource availability. Our findings reveal a generalist pollinator community dominated by bumble bees (45%) and honey bees (26%). By contrast, butterflies, moths, and beetles were notably scarce. However, semi-natural areas, allotments, and cemeteries sustained significant pollinator diversity, which was likely driven by the prevalence of indigenous vegetation and rich floral diversity recorded at these sites.

The plant community in central Edinburgh was primarily comprised of exotic horticultural species, with two-thirds of observed species being non-native. Despite this, the vast majority (87%) of plants recorded were visited by pollinators. Notably, the three plant species found to attract the widest range of pollinator taxa were all indigenous.

As cities continue to densify and expand, these findings emphasize that well connected greenspaces featuring diverse plant communities and indigenous flora are critical components of the green infrastructure necessary to sustain urban pollinator biodiversity.

Introduction

Pollinators are vital to maintaining ecosystem function and agricultural production, with 88% of plant and 75% of crop species dependent on their pollination services (Klein et al. 2007; Ollerton et al., 2011). However, shrinking populations and contracting distributions of many pollinator species have raised concerns regarding the long-term stability of their ecosystem services (e.g. Goulson et al., 2015; Bartomeus et al., 2019). Whilst many causes contribute to ecosystem instability and pollinator declines, there is a consensus that agricultural intensification, urbanisation, climate change, and habitat loss and fragmentation are the among the key drivers (Goulson et al., 2015; Dicks et al., 2021; Janousek et al., 2023).

Urban environments are home to three-quarters of the human population but occupy only 3% of the earth's land (Schiavina et al., 2022). Because of the high densities of impervious surfaces, pollutants and artificial infrastructure, cities comprise novel ecosystems with transformed climates, landscape structures, hydrology and nutrient cycles (Grimm et al., 2008). Despite their limited extent, urban greenspaces can have a significant impact on human health, by increasing well-being, nature education and quality of life (Zhang et al., 2017; Cox et al., 2018). However, these areas can also increase municipal maintenance costs, anti-social behaviour, and,

notably, green gentrification, which displaces low-income residents through rising property values (Maia et al., 2020).

While urbanisation often impoverishes pollinator communities by reducing their species richness and abundance relative to semi-natural habitats (Bergerot et al., 2010; Liang et al., 2023), metropolitan greenspaces can still support significant biodiversity (Hall et al., 2016; Baldock et al., 2019). However, it should be noted that heavily urbanized areas typically exert a severe negative impact across all taxonomic groups (McKinney, 2008). This highlights both the potential opportunities for conservation and the steep challenges biodiversity faces in the heart of major cities.

Urban areas tend to favour generalist pollinators (Wenzel et al. 2020; Silva et al. 2021) while negatively impacting specialists, particularly those with narrow food or habitat requirements (Spotswood et al. 2021). Because urban greenspaces differ widely in their management, structural complexity, and available microhabitats and food sources, their ability to support biodiversity also varies significantly (e.g. Aronson et al. 2017; Gomes et al. 2023). By examining the relationships between pollinators, plants and greenspace management, this report aims to provide actionable guidance on optimising the green infrastructure necessary to Edinburgh's pollinator biodiversity.

Here we quantified the abundance and diversity of flower-visiting insects and flowering plants across central Edinburgh from May to September 2025. This report explores the findings.

Figure 1 A 'Street Planting' site surveyed in 2025, a roundabout at Picardy Place, Edinburgh. Photo: Nicholas Balfour.

Methods

We surveyed 31 sites in central Edinburgh from 20th May to 4th September 2025 between 10am – 4.30pm. Surveys were conducted during weather conditions suitable for all pollinator species, i.e. when temperatures were >11°C and wind speeds below Beaufort scale 5, or 29 km/h (Pywell et al. 2005). Each site was surveyed on three occasions each across the field season: (i) May/June, (ii) June/July, and (iii) August/September.

Sites were organised into seven distinct categories for analysis: (i) five as Botanic Garden, (ii) four as Allotment, (iii) eight Public Garden, (iv) four Street Planting roundabouts and planters; Figure 1), (v) three Semi-Natural, (vi) three Rooftop Garden, and (vii) four Cemetery (Figure 2). The number of censuses per study site was determined by site area. Sites of an area of <1,000 m² we undertook two censuses per visit, four for sites between 1,000-10,000m², and six for sites >10,000 m².

Figure 2 Map of the 31 Edinburgh sites surveyed in 2025. Sites were separated into seven categories: Botanic Garden (dark blue), Allotment (light blue), Public Garden (green) Street Planting (roundabouts, planters; red), Semi-Natural Site (pink), Rooftop Garden (yellow), Cemetery (grey).

Standardised timed censuses were walked under United Kingdom Butterfly Monitoring Scheme conditions (Pollard & Yates, 1993), with all foraging pollinators recorded in a moving virtual box 1m ahead and 1m to each observer's side. The term census is used for pollinator surveys to differentiate them from plant transects. To maximize data acquisition, transects were conducted at locations of the greatest floral density at each site. These locations were subject to change between visits to

ensure comprehensive coverage of peak floral availability. Each census covered a 1 x 10m area and was walked in 2 minutes. The timer was paused when recording or potting specimens. Each census was walked twice per site visit. A 10-min gap between the two repeated censuses allowed disturbed flower-visitors to return (Baldock et al. 2015). Actively foraging pollinators and the flower species they were visiting were recorded. Bees, butterflies, and hoverflies were identified and recorded at species level, and other flies, wasps, and beetles to group level. Specimens were either identified in the field, using field guides (Falk, 2018; Ball and Morris, 2015), or were collected for later identification with the use of a microscope and identification keys (Bot and Meutter, 2023; Else and Edwards, 2018) at RBGE.

All flowering plants within the transect were recorded to the greatest taxonomic resolution possible using a field guide (Streeter et al., 2009) or the smartphone-based plant identification guides PlantNet and Flora Incognita. The number of floral units were counted for each species. A floral unit was defined as an individual flower or collection of flowers following Baldock et al. (2015) - comprising of a single capitulum for Asteraceae (flowers x inflorescence x stems), a secondary umbel for Apiaceae and a single flower for most other taxa. All forbs were sampled regardless of whether they are wind or insect pollinated. Within each transect we also recorded the approximate cover percentage for plant foliage and bare ground.

Results

Pollinator Diversity

Figure 3 Abundance of the main pollinator groups recorded in Edinburgh in 2025, given in percentages.

A total of 3,356 flower-visiting insects were recorded during the three rounds of surveys during 2025. The most commonly recorded groups were bumble bees (45%), followed by honey bees (26%), hoverflies (10%), solitary bees (8%), other flies (6%), beetles (2%) wasps (1%), and butterflies and moths ($\leq 1\%$).

Over 70 species of pollinators were recorded, with the honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) being the most commonly observed. We recorded eight species of bumble bees, 23 solitary bee species, 37 hoverfly species, and only two species of butterflies (*Pieris brassicae* and *Aglais urticae*).

Table 1 Abundance and percentage of the top 30 groups, genera or species recorded in Edinburgh in 2025.

Flower-visitor species/group	Group	Abundance	%
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	honey bee	872	25.98
<i>Bombus lucorum agg.</i>	bumble bee	630	18.77
<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	bumble bee	463	13.80
fly	fly	166	4.95
<i>Bombus lapidarius</i>	bumble bee	131	3.90
<i>Colletes daviesanus</i>	solitary bee	112	3.34
<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	bumble bee	109	3.25
<i>Bombus vestalis</i>	bumble bee	99	2.95
<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	solitary bee	73	2.18
<i>Episyrphus balteatus</i>	hoverfly	71	2.12
<i>Syrphus ribesii</i>	hoverfly	64	1.91
beetle	beetle	57	1.70
<i>Lucilia sp.</i>	fly	49	1.46
<i>Bombus hypnorum</i>	bumble bee	42	1.25
<i>Bombus hortorum</i>	bumble bee	27	0.80
<i>Syrphus vitripennis</i>	hoverfly	25	0.74
wasp	wasp	22	0.66
<i>Erastalis pertinax</i>	hoverfly	19	0.57
<i>Epistrophe grossulariae</i>	hoverfly	18	0.54
<i>Eristalis nemorum</i>	hoverfly	16	0.48
<i>Rhagonycha fulva</i>	beetle	16	0.48
<i>Lassioglossum albipes</i>	solitary bee	15	0.45
hoverfly	hoverfly	15	0.45
<i>Vespula vulgaris</i>	wasp	14	0.42
<i>Myathropa florea</i>	hoverfly	12	0.36
<i>Andrena flavipes</i>	solitary bee	10	0.30
<i>Anthidium manicatum</i>	solitary bee	9	0.27
<i>Megachile centuncularis</i>	solitary bee	9	0.27
<i>Eupeodes luniger</i>	hoverfly	9	0.27
<i>Helophilus pendulus</i>	hoverfly	9	0.27

Plant Diversity

Overall, we recorded 211 species or varieties of plants, of which 183 (87%) were visited by pollinators in our surveys of central Edinburgh greenspaces. Two-thirds (65%) of the plant species recorded were non-native to the United Kingdom. However, the three plant species/varieties (*Leucanthemum vulgare*, *Cirsium arvense* and *Achillea millefolium*) on which we recorded the greatest number of pollinator taxa were all indigenous (Table 2). These species were primarily recorded in Semi-Natural (*A. millefolium*, *L. vulgare*), Cemetery (*A. millefolium*) and Public Garden (*C. arvense*) sites.

Table 2 Top 30 plant species/varieties with the greatest number of pollinator species/groups (left) and total visits (right) recorded in central Edinburgh greenspaces in 2025. Asterisks indicates taxa native to the UK.

Plant	Species/groups	Plant	Visits
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> *	31	<i>Origanum vulgare</i> *	267
<i>Cirsium arvense</i> *	26	<i>Cirsium arvense</i> *	152
<i>Achillea millefolium</i> *	24	<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> *	149
<i>Geranium endressii</i>	17	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> *	135
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> *	17	<i>Nepeta racemosa</i>	112
<i>Senecio squalidus</i>	17	<i>Centaurea nigra</i> *	103
<i>Anaphalis margaritacea</i>	16	<i>Trifolium repens</i> *	103
<i>Centaurea nigra</i> *	16	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i> agg.*	81
<i>Chamaenerion angustifolium</i> *	15	<i>Mentha x villosa</i>	80
<i>Leucanthemum maximum</i>	14	<i>Anaphalis margaritacea</i>	66
<i>Nepeta racemosa</i>	13	<i>Nepeta 'Six Hills Giant'</i>	63
<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i>	13	<i>Geranium endressii</i>	62
<i>Bellis perennis</i> *	12	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	54
<i>Ranunculus acris</i> *	12	<i>Veronica salicifolia</i>	54
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i> *	11	<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	53
<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	10	<i>Origanum laevigatum</i>	49
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i> agg.*	10	<i>Senecio squalidus</i>	47
<i>Buddleja davidii</i>	9	<i>Chamaenerion angustifolium</i> *	43
<i>Trifolium repens</i> *	9	<i>Bellis perennis</i> *	43
<i>Inula helenium</i>	8	<i>Geranium 'Rozanne'</i>	43
<i>Knautia arvensis</i> *	8	<i>Ranunculus acris</i> *	42
<i>Nepeta 'Six Hills Giant'</i>	8	<i>Salvia verticillata 'Purple Rain'</i>	42
<i>Scorzoneroideis autumnalis</i> *	8	<i>Coreopsis verticillata 'Grandiflora'</i>	42
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> *	7	<i>Cynara cardunculus</i>	39
<i>Nepeta x faassenii</i>	7	<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i>	36

Relationship Between Plant and Pollinator Diversity

The data show that flowering plant species diversity is significantly positively related to overall pollinator diversity (Figure 4). A positive relationship was also observed between flowering plant and bee species richness (Spearman's rank correlation: $r = 0.498$, $n = 30$, $p = 0.004$). However, only a weak relationship was observed between

flowering plant and hoverfly species richness (Spearman's rank correlation: $r = 0.331$, $n = 30$, $p = 0.069$).

Figure 4 Relationship between mean flowering plant and pollinator species richness per transect across the study sites. Also shown is a line of best fit (Spearman's rank correlation: $r = 0.573$, $n = 30$, $p < 0.001$).

Pollinator & Plant Diversity Across Site Categories

Figure 5 Mean pollinator (a) abundance and (b) richness per transect across seven site categories. The data is shown for eight pollinator groups: honey bees, bumble bees, wasps, hoverflies, flies, others (beetles, sawflies, bugs and ants) and butterflies and moths.

Pollinator abundance and diversity varied greatly across sites and site categories. The mean abundance per census was approximately three-fold, and species richness two-fold, greater at Allotment, Botanic Garden and Semi-Natural sites than at Rooftop Gardens (Figure 5). Honey bees and bumble bees were dominant across all site categories. The greatest diversity and abundance of Lepidoptera (butterflies

and moths), hoverflies and other pollinator taxa (beetles, sawflies, bugs, ants etc.) were observed at Allotments and Semi-Natural sites.

Allotments had the greatest flowering plant species richness and cover per transect across our study site categories. By contrast, Botanic and Public Garden sites had the lowest species richness per transect, perhaps owing to their relatively large patches of single plant species. We recorded the greatest proportion of non-native plant species at Allotment and Street Planting sites, and relatively low proportions at Semi-Natural, Cemetery and Rooftop Garden sites.

Table 3 Mean flowering plant species richness, percentage cover, and percentage of non-native plant species per transect across the study site categories. The range of site means within each category is provided in brackets.

Category	Species Richness	Cover (%)	Non-Native (%)
Allotment	4.1 (3.4 – 5.2)	52.1 (39 – 71)	60.7 (45 – 72)
Botanic Garden	2.8 (2.5 – 3.0)	35.4 (9 – 58)	54.3 (11 – 100)
Cemetery	3.4 (2.3 – 4.5)	37.7 (28 – 43)	35.9 (0 – 70)
Street Planting	3.0 (1.0 – 3.5)	37.3 (5 – 48)	60.4 (41 – 100)
Public Garden	2.8 (1.6 – 4.2)	37.5 (23 – 61)	46.7 (31 – 86)
Rooftop Garden	3.0 (2.7 – 3.5)	24.0 (20 – 28)	25.6 (11 – 28)
Semi-Natural	3.2 (2.5 – 3.8)	40.0 (33 – 57)	15.8 (8 – 22)

Bee Nesting Behaviours

Figure 6 Bee hotel at the Demonstration Garden, RBGE. Photo: Nicholas Balfour.

A total of 1,675 non-cleptoparasitic wild bees (i.e. non-honeybees) were identified at species level. Of these, 86% were cavity nesters and 14% ground nesters (Table 4). Surprisingly, only one of the 31 study sites hosted a bee hotel, all the nesting tubes of this bee hotel were empty (Figure 6).

Table 4 Bee nesting habits. Bee species and their nesting habit from the Safeguard traits database (Miličić et al., 2023). Renter – nests just below ground in old mammal burrows or in existing cavities of walls, plant stems, or wood. Excavator – excavates burrows in soil and other substrates (mining bees). Cleptoparasite - specialized species that do not build nests or collect pollen, instead laying their eggs in the nests of host bees to utilize their resources.

Species	Abundance	Nesting	Notes
<i>Andrena bicolor</i>	1	excavator	under ground
<i>Andrena denticulata</i>	3	excavator	under ground
<i>Andrena flavipes</i>	10	excavator	under ground
<i>Andrena haemorrhoa</i>	1	excavator	under ground
<i>Andrena scotica</i>	4	excavator	under ground
<i>Anthidium manicatum</i>	9	renter	stems, walls, soil
<i>Anthophora plumipes</i>	3	excavator	above ground
<i>Bombus hortorum</i>	27	renter	under/above ground
<i>Bombus hypnorum</i>	42	renter	above ground
<i>Bombus lapidarius</i>	131	renter	under ground
<i>Bombus muscorum</i>	2	renter	above ground
<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	463	renter	above ground
<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	109	renter	under/above ground
<i>Bombus terrestris</i>	630	renter	under ground
<i>Bombus vestalis</i>	99	cleptoparasite	cleptoparasite
<i>Colletes daviesanus</i>	112	excavator	under ground
<i>Halictus rubicundus</i>	1	excavator	under ground
<i>Heriades truncorum</i>	1	renter	above ground
<i>Hylaeus communis</i>	1	renter/excavator	above ground
<i>Hylaeus hyalinatus</i>	0	renter	under/above ground
<i>Lasioglossum albipes</i>	15	excavator	under ground
<i>Lasioglossum cupromicans</i>	4	excavator	under ground
<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	73	excavator	under ground
<i>Lasioglossum smeathmanellum</i>	8	excavator	under ground
<i>Lasioglossum villosulum</i>	3	excavator	under ground
<i>Megachile centuncularis</i>	9	renter	under/above ground
<i>Megachile willughbiella</i>	8	renter/excavator	under/above ground
<i>Nomada fabriciana</i>	1	cleptoparasite	cleptoparasite
<i>Osmia bicornis</i>	5	renter	under/above ground

Figure 7 *Andrena scotica* guarding her nest from a cleptoparasite (*Nomada marshamella*) on the boundary wall of the RBGE. Photo: Nicholas Balfour.

Case Studies

A. Dean Cemetery

Dean Cemetery is situated in the heart of Edinburgh's historic New Town. While three of the four cemeteries studied in 2025 hosted a relatively high array of flower-visiting taxa, Dean Cemetery was a notable outlier. Here, we recorded half the pollinator abundance and species richness than that found at the other sites in this category. Overall, it hosted just seven pollinator species, with a complete absence of solitary bees, butterflies, moths, and beetles.

Floral diversity at the site was similarly limited, with common daisies (*Bellis perennis*) and buttercups (*Ranunculus* spp.) accounting for two-thirds of all recorded species. This lack of plant variety stemmed from the intensive management of Dean Cemetery, where ground-keeping staff maintained a very closely mown sward (Figure 8).

Research has evidenced that reducing mowing intensity can increase floral resources in urban greenspaces (Morrison and Bright, 2025; Jakobsson et al. 2018; Rudolph et al. 2017). The subsequent increase in floral resources, in turn, improves pollinator community diversity, including butterflies and wild bees, and increases the diversity of rare taxa (Hemmings et al. 2022; Proske et al. 2022).

Conservation in urban areas must balance human needs and expectations with ecological benefits. While there is a growing awareness and support for biodiversity-

friendly measures, the majority of the public still prefer a “well-kept and tidy” appearance (Fischer et al, 2020). However, research also indicates that public approval for long amenity grass increases when it is framed by cues to signify active management, rather than neglect, such as mown borders (Hughes et al., 2025; Garbuzov et al., 2015). It is hoped that engagement with the Trust that own this site could lead to more biodiversity-friendly management of this large (7ha) urban cemetery.

Figure 8 Contrasting sward lengths and resulting floral diversity at (a) Old Calton Cemetery and (b) Dean Cemetery. Photos: Nicholas Balfour.

B. George Square Gardens

George Square Gardens is an urban park situated in front of the Edinburgh University Library. Quiet throughout the year, it transforms into a vibrant Edinburgh Festival Fringe location during August. Although not a particularly ecologically diverse site, it is reasonably well managed for biodiversity. The understory is

infrequently cut during the summer months and plenty of deadwood is left in situ. Multiple species of bees and wasps were recorded nesting in decaying tree trunks at this site. Thus, highlighting the value of decaying wood in urban greenspaces as a valuable nesting resource for many flower-visiting insects (Ranalli et al., 2025).

In mid-July a very surprising bee was collected at George Square Gardens - *Heriades truncorum* (Figure 9). This solitary, wood-nesting species is endemic to central Europe and is a pollen specialist on Asteraceae plants (Praz et al., 2008). In the United Kingdom it is primarily associated with the south-east of England, particularly the commons of Surrey. Historically considered scarce, *H. truncorum* has never previously been recorded north of Shropshire. As such, this represents the first record of the species in Scotland. While it has been spreading northward in response to the warmer late summers of recent decades (Edwards, 2012), its arrival in Edinburgh may exemplify a climate-mediated range expansion via 'urban jumping.' This process occurs when the urban heat island effect creates a microclimatic 'stepping stone,' enabling thermophilic species to bypass unsuitable rural landscapes and colonise northern urban centres ahead of the wider regional population (Banaszak-Cibicka, 2014).

Figure 9 A female large headed resin bee (*Heriades truncorum*) collected at George Square Edinburgh. Photo: Nicholas Balfour.

The female of the genus utilizes pre-existing holes, often in dead wood, such as old beetle galleries, and seals the individual cells of her nest with tree resin and small

bits of grit. Hence, their common name - resin bees. Interestingly, *H. truncorum* has also been observed to nest in cavities of construction timber. Which raises the question – could this bee have hitched a ride north in the plethora of construction timber that is brought to this site every August for the Edinburgh Festival Fringe?

This site was covered with big top tents, bars, food trucks and festival goers two weeks after the bee was collected (Figure 10). It will be interesting to see if this species is still present at this site in 2026 or if this was a one-off vagrant, well beyond its known range.

Figure 10 George Square Gardens during the Edinburgh Festival. Photo: Chris Scott.

C. Royal Botanic Gardens, Edinburgh

The RBGE is home to one of the largest and richest plant collections on Earth. While it does include a few small semi-natural areas filled with indigenous flora, on the whole it is devoted to non-native taxa. The most important plants for pollinators tend to be ‘weedy’ native species (e.g. thistles, ragworts, hogweed; Balfour et al., 2022). However, many horticultural varieties can also play an important role in supporting pollinator communities (Erickson et al., 2021).

One ornamental plant species at this location attracted a wide variety of pollinator species: *Anaphalis margaritacea* (Pearly everlasting; Figure 11). This perennial herb is native to Asia and North America and in the family Asteraceae. On a single patch

(~5m²) of this plant, 11 pollinator species were recorded (three solitary bee species, butterflies, wasps, hoverflies) during one census. This plant has papery white flowers with yellow centres with disk florets, and short, accessible corolla tubes. As such the nectaries of this species are easily accessible to a range of pollinators, even those with short-tongues like flies, wasps and many social bee species (e.g. Balfour et al., 2021).

From this winter the RBGE is implementing an ecologically enhanced overwintering management strategy. This protocol involves increasing vegetation cutting height and retaining leaf litter as natural mulch to preserve structural refugia. Additionally, the construction of dead hedges within the understory aims to provide overwintering microhabitats for invertebrate assemblages. These interventions are to be complemented by a diversification of their pollinator-friendly plant species.

Figure 11 A batman hoverfly (*Myathropa florea*), recognisable by the dark markings on its thorax that resemble the Batman logo, foraging on pearly everlasting (*Anaphalis margaritacea*). Photo: Nicholas Balfour.

Discussion

Our findings revealed a generalist pollinator community in central Edinburgh greenspaces, dominated by bumble bees (45%) and honey bees (26%). By contrast, butterflies (<1%), moths (<1%), and beetles (2%) were notably scarce. One potential reason for the small number of butterfly and moth observed is that this study focused exclusively on flower-visiting individuals, whereas these species are more commonly recorded while in flight. Additionally, butterfly foraging is strictly limited by abiotic

conditions (temperature and wind; Balfour and Ratnieks, 2025), and most British moth species are nocturnal.

Urban areas have been shown to favour generalist pollinator species (Wenzel et al. 2020; Silva et al. 2021) and negatively impact specialists, particularly those with narrow food plant or habitat requirements (Spotswood et al. 2021). This trend is often more prevalent in highly urbanised environments, where habitat patches are extremely isolated and fragmented by the surrounding urban matrix (e.g. Fortel et al., 2014; Wenzel et al., 2020).

The absence of the northern brown argus (*Aricia artaxerxes*) in our surveys highlights this phenomenon. This is a focal species for both the Edinburgh Biodiversity Action Plan and the broader Pollinator Strategy for Scotland. Despite targeted management and planting within Edinburgh and the presence of its larval food plant (*Helianthemum nummularium*) at our study sites, it remains extremely rare in Edinburgh outside of one Site of Special Scientific Interest (Holyrood Park).

Despite this, pollinator diversity remained relatively high at several sites, notably semi-natural areas, allotments, and cemeteries, which hosted a broader array of flower-visiting taxa (Figure 3). Notably, the majority of butterfly and moth species were recorded at semi-natural sites. This is attributable to the availability of larval host plants at these sites, such as common nettle (*Urtica dioica*). In line with these patterns, previous research in Edinburgh and three other British cities (Bristol, Reading, and Leeds) indicated that allotments and cemeteries are the urban land categories which support the greatest levels of pollinator diversity and abundance (Baldock et al., 2019).

The Effect of Plant Diversity

The pollinator richness in allotments and cemeteries may be attributed to high flowering-plant abundance, the presence of native plant species, relatively low-intensity management, and proximity to extensive semi-natural habitats. Overall, plant diversity was positively related to pollinator diversity, particularly for bees, suggesting that floral diversity is a key driver of pollinator richness at our sites (Baldock et al., 2015; Hyjazie and Sargent, 2022).

In central Edinburgh, non-native species accounted for two-thirds (65%) of the flora. This dominance of non-native flowering plants aligns with patterns observed in other British urban areas (Smith et al., 2006; Grace, 2025). While our data suggest that both native and non-native plants serve as vital urban foraging resources, it is notable that the three species attracting the broadest range of pollinator taxa were all indigenous (*Leucanthemum vulgare*, *Cirsium arvense*, and *Achillea millefolium*). This pattern reinforces evidence that native plant species often play a disproportionate role in supporting diverse pollinator assemblages in urban and semi-natural habitats (Salisbury et al., 2015; Lilkendey et al., 2025). This may be because of their shared

evolutionary histories that shape floral traits, phenology, and reward composition (e.g. Mitchell et al., 2009).

Non-native garden plants often provide limited support for specialized wildlife, particularly herbivorous insects with narrow dietary requirements (Dyer et al. 2007). While these plants may still provide valuable nectar and pollen resources for generalist pollinators (Salisbury et al., 2015; Seitz et al., 2020), horticultural modifications, such as the "doubling" of petals in peonies, dahlias, and roses, frequently restrict access to, or reduce the volume, of floral rewards (Corbet et al. 2001). Notably, several of the cultivars on which we did not record any flower-visitors in this study were double petalled: *Rosa sempervirens*, *Paeonia* sp., *Rosa* 'Olivia Rose Austin', *Scabiosa columbaria* 'Dwarf Blue', and *Dianthus barbatus* (cultivated variety).

Site Management and Interventions

Since their adoption of the Living Landscape Initiative, which aims to make Edinburgh one of the most sustainable in Europe by 2050, the City of Edinburgh Council mows its recreational spaces every two to three weeks and other areas every six weeks to promote more wildlife-friendly habitats. Our data demonstrate that this approach materially enhances pollinator habitats, as evidenced by CEC-managed cemeteries having twice the pollinator abundance and species richness than a heavily manicured, trust-managed cemetery. Reducing mowing intensity in urban spaces is a critical management strategy for supporting pollinator biodiversity. Research indicates that transitioning from high-intensity to low-intensity mowing (typically twice or fewer times per year) can increase flower-visiting insect abundance by up to five times (Garbuzov et al., 2015).

Urban Filtering and Pollinator Assemblages

The low proportion of ground nesting bees recorded suggests an 'urban filtering' effect. In a dense city centre like Edinburgh, extensive impervious surfaces (tarmac, concrete, and paving) and highly managed, compacted soils severely limit the bare, well-drained earth that mining bees require (Cepukaitè et al. 2025). This suggests that increasing floral resources alone may be insufficient to maximise bee community diversity unless accompanied by the provision of suitable nesting substrates, such as undisturbed patches of bare soil or bee nesting banks.

Honey Bees in the Urban Context

Honey bees (*A. mellifera*) constituted a high proportion of the pollinators recorded in central Edinburgh (26%). Baldock et al. (2015) surveyed four UK cities and recorded an average of 11% honey bees across four UK cities, while Plant et al. (2025), recorded an average of 7% across the Glasgow in 2023. Individuals and businesses often assume they can help pollinator declines by installing honey bee colonies in gardens or on rooftops, a perception reinforced by commercial "adopt-a-hive" and urban beekeeping initiatives that frame hive ownership as a conservation action

(Alton & Ratnieks, 2016). Consequently, managed colony numbers have increased rapidly in cities such as London and Edinburgh, contributing to unusually high densities of honey bees (Alton & Ratnieks, 2016; Stevenson et al., 2020). However, this overlooks that pollinator conservation is generally more effective when focused on habitat enhancement and nesting provision rather than increasing hive density.

Managed honey bees can exert significant ecological pressures on wild pollinator communities through both exploitative competition and pest and pathogen spillover. High densities of managed colonies often deplete shared floral resources (nectar and pollen), reducing foraging efficiency, reproductive success, and population densities of other pollinators, particularly in fragmented habitats (Pasquali et al., 2025). In parallel, honey bees act as reservoirs and vectors for a range of pathogens and parasites, which can be transmitted to wild pollinators via shared flowers (Graystock et al., 2015; Manley et al., 2015).

Conclusion

Pollinators are essential for both ecosystem function and crop production but are under increasing pressure. Although central Edinburgh supports a diverse and abundant pollinator community, it is dominated by generalist species. Enhancing floral diversity and nesting resources in urban green spaces would help support a wider range of taxa, particularly specialist species, while improving connectivity between sites could facilitate pollinator movement. Efforts should prioritise diverse, pollinator-friendly planting and the provision of nesting habitats for both cavity- and ground-nesting species. Maintaining a sustainable balance between managed honey bees and wild pollinators is also important in resource-limited urban environments, alongside raising awareness through collaboration with local councils, schools, and community groups.

Because pollinators navigate a complex mosaic of nesting and floral sites, urban conservation requires an integrated, landscape-scale approach rather than isolated interventions. These findings highlight the significant variability in floral resources across urban land-use types, the importance of native plant species and underscore the need for targeted city management to increase habitat connectivity.

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References

- Alton, K. and Ratnieks, F., 2016. Roof top hives: Practical beekeeping or publicity stunt? *Bee World*, 93, 64-67.
- Aronson, M.F., Piana, M.R., MacIvor, J.S. and Pregitzer, C.C., 2017. Management of plant diversity in urban green spaces. *Urban Biodiversity*, 101-120.
- Baldock, K.C., Goddard, M.A., Hicks, D.M., Kunin, W.E., Mitschunas, N., Osgathorpe, L.M., Potts, S.G., Robertson, K.M., Scott, A.V., Stone, G.N. and Vaughan, I.P., 2015. Where is the UK's pollinator biodiversity? The importance of urban areas for flower-visiting insects. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282.
- Baldock, K.C., Goddard, M.A., Hicks, D.M., Kunin, W.E., Mitschunas, N., Morse, H., Osgathorpe, L.M., Potts, S.G., Robertson, K.M., Scott, A.V. and Staniczenko, P.P., 2019. A systems approach reveals urban pollinator hotspots and conservation opportunities. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 3, 363-373.
- Balfour, N.J., Shackleton, K., Arscott, N.A., Roll-Baldwin, K., Bracuti, A., Toselli, G. and Ratnieks, F.L., 2021. Energetic efficiency of foraging mediates bee niche partitioning, 102, e03285.
- Balfour, N.J. and Ratnieks, F.L., 2022. The disproportionate value of 'weeds' to pollinators and biodiversity. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 59, 1209-1218.
- Balfour, N.J. and Ratnieks, F.L., 2025. Wind Alters Plant-Pollinator Community Structure, Bee Foraging Rate & Movements Between Plants. *Behavioral Ecology*, araf067.
- Ball, S., Morris, R. 2015. *Britain's Hoverflies*. Princeton University Press
- Banaszak-Cibicka, W., 2014. Are urban areas suitable for thermophilic and xerothermic bee species (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Apiformes)? *Apidologie*, 45, 145-155.
- Bartomeus, I., Stavert, J.R., Ward, D. and Aguado, O., 2019. Historical collections as a tool for assessing the global pollination crisis. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 374, 20170389.
- Bates, A.J., Sadler, J.P., Fairbrass, A.J., Falk, S.J., Hale, J.D. and Matthews, T.J., 2011. Changing bee and hoverfly pollinator assemblages along an urban-rural gradient. *PLoS One*, 6, e23459.
- Bergerot, B., Fontaine, B., Renard, M., Cadi, A. and Julliard, R., 2010. Preferences for exotic flowers do not promote urban life in butterflies. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 96, 98-107.
- Bot, S. and Meutter, F.V.D., 2023. *Hoverflies of Britain and North-west Europe*. Bloomsbury Wildlife.

- Cepukaitè, I., Björkén, A., Widenfalk, L.A., Jonsell, M. and Locke, B., 2025. Environmental factors influencing ground-nesting bee communities in an urban landscape: implications for conservation. *Urban Ecosystems*, 28, 97.
- Corbet, S.A., Bee, J., Dasmahapatra, K., Gale, S., Gorringe, E., La Ferla, B. et al. 2001. Native or exotic? Double or single? Evaluating plants for pollinator-friendly gardens. *Annals of Botany*, 87, 219–232.
- Cox, D.T., Shanahan, D.F., Hudson, H.L., Fuller, R.A. and Gaston, K.J., 2018. The impact of urbanisation on nature dose and the implications for human health. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 179, 72-80.
- Dicks LV, Breeze TD, Ngo HT, Senapathi D, An J, Aizen MA, Basu P, Buchori D, Galetto L, Garibaldi LA, and Gemmill-Herren B. 2021. A global-scale expert assessment of drivers and risks associated with pollinator decline. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1453-61.
- Dyer, L.A., Singer, M.S., Lill, J.T., Stireman, J.O., Gentry, G.L., Marquis, R.J. et al. 2007. Host specificity of Lepidoptera in tropical and temperate forests. *Nature*, 448, 696–699.
- Edwards, M. 2012. *Heriades truncorum*. Bees, Wasps and Ants Recording Society (BWARS) Website. <https://bwars.com/bee/megachilidae/heriades-truncorum>
- Else, G.R. and Edwards, M., 2018. Handbook of the Bees of the British Isles (2-Volume Set). Ray Society, UK.
- Erickson, E., Patch, H.M. and Grozinger, C.M., 2021. Herbaceous perennial ornamental plants can support complex pollinator communities. *Scientific reports*, 11, 17352.
- Falk, S. 2018. Field Guide to the Bees of Great Britain and Ireland. Bloomsbury Publishing
- Fischer, L.K., Neuenkamp, L., Lampinen, J., Tuomi, M., Alday, J.G., Bucharova, A., Cancellieri, L., Casado-Arzuaga, I., Čeplová, N., Cerveró, L. and Deák, B., 2020. Public attitudes toward biodiversity-friendly greenspace management in Europe. *Conservation Letters*, 13, e12718.
- Fortel, L., Henry, M., Guilbaud, L., Guirao, A.L., Kuhlmann, M., Mouret, H., Rollin, O., and Vaissière, B.E., 2014. Decreasing abundance, increasing diversity and changing structure of the wild bee community (Hymenoptera: Anthophila) along an urbanization gradient. *PLoS One*, 9.
- Garbuzov, M., Fensome, K.A. and Ratnieks, F.L., 2015. Public approval plus more wildlife: twin benefits of reduced mowing of amenity grass in a suburban public park in Saltdean, UK. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*, 8, 107-119.

- Gomes, I.N., Bosenbecker C., Silva V.H.D., Cardoso J.C.F., Pena J.C., Maruyama P.K., 2023. Spatiotemporal availability of pollinator attractive trees in a tropical streetscape: unequal distribution for pollinators and people. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 83.
- Goulson, D., Nicholls, E., Botías, C. and Rotheray, E.L., 2015. Bee declines driven by combined stress from parasites, pesticides, and lack of flowers. *Science*, 347, 1255957.
- Grace, J., 2025. The remarkable species richness of the urban flora of Scotland. *Plant Ecology & Diversity*, 5-6, 317-330.
- Graystock, P., Goulson, D. and Hughes, W.O., 2015. Parasites in bloom: flowers aid dispersal and transmission of pollinator parasites within and between bee species. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282, 20151371.
- Grimm, N.B., Faeth, S.H., Golubiewski, N.E., Redman, C.L., Wu, J., Bai, X. and Briggs, J.M., 2008. Global change and the ecology of cities. *Science*, 319, 756-760.
- Han, Q., Keeffe, G., Caplat, P. and Simson, A., 2021. Cities as hot stepping stones for tree migration. *NPJ Urban Sustainability*, 1, 12.
- Hemmings, K., Elton, R. and Grange, I., 2022. No-mow amenity grassland case study: Phenology of floral abundance and nectar resource. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence*, 3, e12179.
- Hughes, J.P., Lengieza, M. and Knight, G., 2025. Beauty not Sustainability: Support for mowing and rewilding is most influenced by subjective visual appeal not ecological friendliness. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 113, 129076.
- Janousek, W.M., Douglas, M.R., Cannings, S., Clément, M.A., Delphia, C.M., Everett, J.G., Hatfield, R.G., Keinath, D.A., Koch, J.B.U., McCabe, L.M. and Mola, J.M., 2023. Recent and future declines of a historically widespread pollinator linked to climate, land cover, and pesticides. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120, e2211223120.
- Klein, A.M., Vaissière, B.E., Cane, J.H., Steffan-Dewenter, I., Cunningham, S.A., Kremen, C. and Tscharntke, T., 2007. Importance of pollinators in changing landscapes for world crops. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 274, 303-313.
- Liang, H., He, Y.D., Theodorou, P. and Yang, C.F., 2023. The effects of urbanization on pollinators and pollination: A meta-analysis. *Ecology Letters*, 26, 1629-1642.
- Lilkendey, T., Mason, B.M., Pernat, N., Marquis, M., Francis, J.S. and Callaghan, C.T., 2025. Proportion of native plants is a key predictor of pollinator richness in urban greenspaces. *Urban Ecosystems*, 28, 233.

- Maia, A.T.A., Calcagni, F., Connolly, J.J.T., Anguelovski, I. and Langemeyer, J., 2020. Hidden drivers of social injustice: uncovering unequal cultural ecosystem services behind green gentrification. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 112, 254-263.
- McKinney, M.L., 2008. Effects of urbanization on species richness: a review of plants and animals. *Urban ecosystems*, 11, 161-176.
- Miličić, M., Vujić, A., and Sentil, A. 2023. Open database on traits and phylogenetic data on European pollinators [Data set]. Zenodo.
- Mitchell, R.J., Irwin, R.E., Flanagan, R.J. and Karron, J.D., 2009. Ecology and evolution of plant–pollinator interactions. *Annals of botany*, 103, 1355-1363.
- Morrison, M.A. and Bright, A., 2025. Reduced mowing frequencies increase pollinator abundance in urban lawns in the UK. *Conservation Evidence*, 22, 1-8.
- Ollerton, J., Winfree, R. and Tarrant, S. 2011. How many flowering plants are pollinated by animals? *Oikos*, 120, 321-326.
- Pasquali, L., Bruschini, C., Benetello, F., Bonifacino, M., Giannini, F., Monterastelli, E., Penco, M., Pesarini, S., Salvati, V., Simbula, G. and Volponi, M.S., 2025. Island-wide removal of honeybees reveals exploitative trophic competition with strongly declining wild bee populations. *Current Biology*, 35, 1576-1590.
- Plant, E., Dunkley, R., Dominoni, D.M. and McCafferty, D.J., 2025. Supporting pollinators in urban gardens: floral richness and abundance influence flower visitor interactions regardless of the surrounding landscape. *Urban Ecosystems*, 28, 235.
- Potts SG, Robertson KM, Scott A V., Stone GN, Vaughan IP, and Memmott J. 2015. Where is the UK's pollinator biodiversity? The importance of urban areas for flower-visiting insects. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282.
- Praz, C.J., Müller, A. and Dorn, S. 2008. Specialized bees fail to develop on non-host pollen: do plants chemically protect their pollen. *Ecology*, 89, 795–804.
- Proske, A., Lokatis, S. and Rolff, J., 2022. Impact of mowing frequency on arthropod abundance and diversity in urban habitats: a meta-analysis. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 76, 127714.
- Ranalli, R., Galimberti, A., Labra, M. and Biella, P., 2025. Forest spatial configuration and local management influence bee pollinator biodiversity in urban and rural landscapes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 377, 124672.
- Rudolph, M., Velbert, F., Schwenzfeier, S., Kleinebecker, T. and Klaus, V.H., 2017. Patterns and potentials of plant species richness in high-and low-maintenance urban grasslands. *Applied Vegetation Science*, 20, 18-27.
- Salisbury, A., Armitage, J., Bostock, H., Perry, J., Tatchell, M. and Thompson, K., 2015. Enhancing gardens as habitats for flower-visiting aerial insects (pollinators): should we plant native or exotic species?. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52,1156-1164.

Schiavina M, Melchiorri M, Pesaresi M, Politis P, Freire S, et al. 2022. GHSL Data Package 2022. Luxembourg: Publ. Off. Eur. Union.

Seitz, N., Vanengelsdorp, D. and Leonhardt, S.D., 2020. Are native and non-native pollinator friendly plants equally valuable for native wild bee communities?. *Ecology and evolution*, 10, 12838-12850.

Seto, K.C., S. Parnell, and T. Elmqvist. 2013. A global outlook on urbanization. In *Urbanization, biodiversity and ecosystem services: Challenges and opportunities, A global assessment*, ed. T. Elmqvist, M. Fragkias, J. Goodness, B. Guneralp, P.J. Marcotullio, R.I. McDonald, S. Parnell, M. Scheweniius, et al. London: Springer.

Smith, R.M., Thompson, K., Hodgson, J.G., Warren, P.H. and Gaston, K.J., 2006. Urban domestic gardens (IX): composition and richness of the vascular plant flora, and implications for native biodiversity. *Biological Conservation*, 129, 312-322.

Spotswood, E.N., Beller, E.E., Grossinger, R., Grenier, J.L., Heller, N.E. and Aronson, M.F., 2021. The biological deserts fallacy: cities in their landscapes contribute more than we think to regional biodiversity. *BioScience*, 71, 148-160.

Stevenson, P.C., Bidartondo, M.I., Blackhall-Miles, R., Cavagnaro, T.R., Cooper, A., Geslin, B., Koch, H., Lee, M.A., Moat, J., O'hanlon, R. and Sjöman, H., 2020. The state of the world's urban ecosystems: What can we learn from trees, fungi, and bees? *Plants, People, Planet*, 2, 482-498.

Streeter, D., Hart-Davies, C., Hardcastle, A., Cole, F. and Harper, L. 2009. *Collins Flower Guide*. Collins.

Tonietto, R.K. and Larkin, D.J., 2018. Habitat restoration benefits wild bees: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 55, 582-590.

Wenzel, A., I. Grass, V.V. Belavadi, and T. Tschardt. 2020. How urbanization is driving pollinator diversity and pollination: A systematic review. *Biological Conservation* 241, 108321.

Zhang, L., Tan, P.Y. and Diehl, J.A., 2017. A conceptual framework for studying urban green spaces effects on health. *Journal of Urban Ecology*, 3, jux015.

Appendix 1 List of sites surveyed for flower-visiting insects and habitats in 2025 and their coordinates.

Site	Coordinates
Allotment	
Dean Gallery Allotments	55.95164, -3.22520
East Scotland Street Lane Allotment	55.96018, -3.19423
Inverleith Allotments	55.96408, -3.21984
India Place Allotments	55.95598, -3.20978
Botanic Garden	
Demonstration Garden	55.96678, -3.21120
Living Lawn	55.96351, -3.20972
Queen Mother's Garden	55.96713, -3.21044
Western Border	55.96640, -3.21145
Wild Wood	55.96647, -3.21282
Cemetery	
Dean Cemetery	55.95308, -3.22168
Greyfriars Kirk Cemetery	55.94691, -3.19283
Old Calton Cemetery	55.95365, -3.18583
St John's Church Cemetery	55.95009, -3.20561
Street Planting	
Broughton Street Roundabout	55.95930, -3.19091
Picardy Place Roundabout	55.95662, -3.18687
Princess Street Planters	55.95201, -3.19598
Public Garden	
Royal Mile Planters	55.95015, -3.18766
Atholl Crescent Gardens	55.94820, -3.21201
Calton Hill Observatory	55.95483, -3.18349
Dunbar Close Gardens	55.95207, -3.17893
George Square Gardens	55.94365, -3.18881
Nicholson Square Gardens	55.94601, -3.18539
Princess Street Gardens East	55.95187, -3.19372
St Mary's Cathedral Gardens	55.94885, -3.21725
St Andrews Square Gardens	55.95421, -3.19313
Rooftop Garden	
Edinburgh Council Roof Garden	55.95228, -3.18387
GPO Roof Garden	55.95329, -3.18805
National Museum Roof Garden	55.94686, -3.19033
Semi-Natural	
Scottish Parliament	55.95118, -3.17337
Water of Leith North	55.96261, -3.20582
Water of Leith South	55.95235, -3.22209